

HOME-BASED FARMING IN TEACHING TECHNOLOGY AND LIVELIHOOD EDUCATION AND THE ACHIEVEMENT IN HORTICULTURE OF GRADE 9 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Horticulture is the science and craft of maintaining, promoting, and using intricately developed food and decorative plants. It specializes in growing crops for growing plants that are beneficial for medical purposes or decorative and ornamental purposes. Furthermore, crops and plants provide a means of regulating and creating oxygen which therefore also minimizes the carbon dioxide in the environment. The emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic has led people to start home-based planting of crops due to the possible dangers of food instability as people are now forced on their homes to minimize the spread of the disease (Dongyu, 2020). In connection to this, schools were also forced to close and continue the academic development of the students through modular distance learning which affected TLE students that specializes in performing skill-based learning. Thus, the researcher developed the study to assess the effectiveness of home-based farming in teaching technology and livelihood education and evaluate the competencies in horticulture of the Grade 9 students in San Antonio National High School S.Y. 2020-2021. Wherein, the researcher used a descriptive correlated type of research design to proceed with the study. Based on the findings of the study, there is no significant relationship between the home-based farming skills and the assessment of the psychomotor skills of the respondents and there is also no significant relationship between the home-based farming skills and the achievement in horticulture competencies of the respondents.

Keywords: Horticulture, home-based planting, skill-based learning, psychomotor skills